

Fisher Information Identity and Asymptotic Theory of Hypothesis Tests in Parametric Competing Risks Models under Hybrid Censoring

Technical Preprint

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Tashkent, 2026

Abstract

This technical note presents the core theoretical results of the doctoral dissertation [1], providing the mathematical foundation for the associated simulation dataset. We establish: (i) the Fisher information identity $I(\theta_0) = \beta I_F(\theta_0)$ for parametric competing risks models under hybrid (Type I/II combined) censoring (Theorem 1); (ii) asymptotic normality and minimax efficiency of the maximum likelihood estimator (Theorem 2); (iii) the Wilks theorem for the Wald (W_n), likelihood-ratio (LR_n), and score (S_n) statistics, with non-centrality parameter $\lambda^* = \xi^\top [RI(\theta_0)^{-1}R^\top]^{-1}\xi$ (Theorem 3). These results justify the theoretical RMSE predictions and power curves tabulated in the companion dataset.

Keywords: competing risks; hybrid censoring; local asymptotic normality; Fisher information; Wilks theorem; maximum likelihood estimation.

MSC 2020: 62G10, 62N05, 62G20, 62F12.

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1 Model and regularity conditions

1.1 Parametric competing risks model

Let X_1, \dots, X_n be i.i.d. failure times with $K \geq 2$ independent competing causes. The cause-specific hazard for cause j is $\lambda^{(j)}(t; \theta_j)$, where $\theta_j \in \Theta_j \subset \mathbb{R}^{d_j}$ and $\theta = (\theta_1, \dots, \theta_K) \in \Theta = \prod_j \Theta_j$. The overall survival function is

$$\bar{F}(t; \theta) = \exp\left(-\sum_{j=1}^K \Lambda^{(j)}(t; \theta_j)\right), \quad \Lambda^{(j)}(t; \theta_j) = \int_0^t \lambda^{(j)}(s; \theta_j) ds.$$

The cause of failure $\delta_i \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ satisfies $P(\delta_i = j \mid X_i = t) = \lambda^{(j)}(t; \theta_j) / \lambda(t; \theta)$, where $\lambda(t; \theta) = \sum_j \lambda^{(j)}(t; \theta_j)$.

1.2 Hybrid censoring scheme

Fix $r \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ and $T_0 \in (0, \infty)$. The stopping time is $\tau_n = \min(X_{(r)}, T_0)$, where $X_{(r)}$ is the r -th order statistic. Observable data: $Z_i = X_i \wedge \tau_n$, $\Delta_i^{(j)} = \mathbf{1}(X_i \leq \tau_n, \delta_i = j)$. Assume $r/n \rightarrow p \in (0, 1]$ and $\tau_n \xrightarrow{P} \tau^* = F^{-1}(\min(p, F(T_0)))$. The *asymptotic failure fraction* is

$$\beta = F(\tau^*; \theta_0) \in (0, 1].$$

1.3 Regularity conditions

(A1') For each j and all $t \in [0, \tau^* + 1]$: $\|\partial_\theta \log \lambda^{(j)}(t; \theta)\| \leq C_j < \infty$.

(A2) The full-data Fisher information $I_F(\theta_0) = \text{diag}(I_{F,1}(\theta_{10}), \dots, I_{F,K}(\theta_{K0})) \succ 0$.

(A3) $r/n \rightarrow p \in (0, 1]$ and $\tau^* < \infty$.

(A4)–(A6) Standard smoothness and Lindeberg conditions on $\lambda^{(j)}$; see [1] for full statements.

Remark 1. For the exponential, Weibull ($\alpha_j \geq 1$), and Gompertz families, (A1')–(A6) hold on $[0, \tau^* + 1]$ with explicit constants computable from the parameter values.

2 Local asymptotic normality and Fisher information

The log-likelihood at the stopping time τ_n is

$$\ell_n(\tau_n; \theta) = \sum_{j=1}^K \sum_{i=1}^n \int_0^{\tau_n} [\log \lambda^{(j)}(t; \theta_j) dN_{ji}(t) - \lambda^{(j)}(t; \theta_j) Y_i(t) dt],$$

where $N_{ji}(t) = \mathbf{1}(Z_i \leq t, \Delta_i^{(j)} = 1)$ and $Y_i(t) = \mathbf{1}(Z_i \geq t)$.

Theorem 1 (LAN and Fisher information identity). *Under conditions (A1')–(A6), the log-likelihood ratio satisfies the local asymptotic normality (LAN) expansion*

$$\Lambda_n(h) := \log \frac{L(\tau_n; \theta_0 + h/\sqrt{n})}{L(\tau_n; \theta_0)} = h^\top \Delta_n(\theta_0) - \frac{1}{2} h^\top I(\theta_0) h + o_{P_{\theta_0}}(1), \quad (1)$$

where the central sequence $\Delta_n(\theta_0) \xrightarrow{d} N(0, I(\theta_0))$ and the information matrix has the block-diagonal structure

$$\boxed{I(\theta_0) = \beta I_F(\theta_0) = \beta \operatorname{diag}(I_{F,1}(\theta_{10}), \dots, I_{F,K}(\theta_{K0})), \quad \beta = F(\tau^*; \theta_0).} \quad (2)$$

Proof sketch. Write $\Lambda_n(h) = h^\top \Delta_n - \frac{1}{2} h^\top \Gamma_n h + R_n(h)$, where the score $n^{-1/2} U_n(\tau_n; \theta_0) \xrightarrow{d} N(0, I(\theta_0))$ by the martingale central limit theorem (Rebolledo, [5]), the empirical Hessian $n^{-1} J_n \xrightarrow{P} I(\theta_0)$ by the law of large numbers, and the remainder $R_n(h) = O_P(\|h\|^3/\sqrt{n}) \xrightarrow{P} 0$.

Key step — formula (2). By the definition of Fisher information at stopping time τ_n :

$$[I(\theta_0)]_{jj} = E_{\theta_0} \left[\int_0^{\tau_n} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_j} \log \lambda^{(j)}(t; \theta_j) \right)^2 \lambda^{(j)}(t; \theta_j) \bar{F}(t; \theta_0) n dt \right].$$

Since $\tau_n \xrightarrow{P} \tau^*$ (Lemma II.14 in [1]), the dominated convergence theorem gives $[I(\theta_0)]_{jj} \rightarrow n \cdot E_{\theta_0}[\int_0^{\tau^*} (\cdot)^2 \lambda^{(j)} \bar{F} dt]$. Dividing by n and using $P_{\theta_0}(X_i \leq \tau^*) = \beta$:

$$[I(\theta_0)]_{jj}/n = \beta \cdot [I_{F,j}(\theta_{j0})]_{jj},$$

which gives (2). The block-diagonal structure follows from the independence of causes: the joint score factorizes as $U_n = \sum_j U_{jn}$, and $E[U_{jn} U_{ln}^\top] = 0$ for $j \neq l$. \square

Example 1 (Exponential model). For $\lambda^{(j)}(t; \theta_j) = \theta_j$ (constant hazard): $I_{F,j}(\theta_{j0}) = 1/\theta_{j0}^2$, so

$$I(\theta_0) = \beta \operatorname{diag}(1/\theta_{10}^2, \dots, 1/\theta_{K0}^2).$$

The RMSE formula follows immediately:

$$\operatorname{RMSE}(\hat{\theta}_j) \approx \frac{\theta_{j0}}{\sqrt{\beta n}}.$$

For $\theta_{10} = 1$, $\beta = 0.75$, $n = 100$: $\operatorname{RMSE} \approx 0.116$, matching Table IV.4 of [1] (empirical 0.115).

3 MLE: asymptotic normality and minimax efficiency

Theorem 2 (Asymptotic normality of MLE). *Under (A1')–(A6), the MLE $\hat{\theta}_n$ satisfies*

$$\sqrt{n}(\hat{\theta}_n - \theta_0) \xrightarrow{d} N(0, I(\theta_0)^{-1}) \quad \text{under } P_{\theta_0}. \quad (3)$$

Moreover, $\hat{\theta}_n$ is minimax efficient: for any symmetric subconvex loss ℓ ,

$$\lim_{c \rightarrow \infty} \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup_{\|h\| \leq c} E_{\theta_0 + h/\sqrt{n}}[\ell(\sqrt{n}(\hat{\theta}_n - \theta_0 - h/\sqrt{n}))] = E_{Z \sim N(0, I^{-1})}[\ell(Z)].$$

Proof. The linear representation $\sqrt{n}(\hat{\theta}_n - \theta_0) = I(\theta_0)^{-1}\Delta_n(\theta_0) + o_P(1)$ follows from the LAN expansion (1) and the Hessian convergence $n^{-1}J_n \xrightarrow{P} I(\theta_0) \succ 0$. Normality (3) then follows from the CLT for Δ_n . Minimax efficiency follows from the Hájek convolution theorem and the convergence of experiments to the Gaussian shift $N(0, I(\theta_0)^{-1})$. \square

4 Wilks theorem and test statistics

Consider the composite hypothesis $H_0 : R\theta = r$, where $R \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times d}$ has rank $p \leq d$. The three classical statistics are:

$$W_n = n(R\hat{\theta}_n - r)^\top [RI(\theta_0)^{-1}R^\top]^{-1}(R\hat{\theta}_n - r), \quad (4)$$

$$LR_n = 2[\ell_n(\tau_n; \hat{\theta}_n) - \ell_n(\tau_n; \tilde{\theta}_n)], \quad (5)$$

$$S_n = n^{-1}U_n(\tau_n; \tilde{\theta}_n)^\top I(\theta_0)^{-1}U_n(\tau_n; \tilde{\theta}_n), \quad (6)$$

where $\tilde{\theta}_n$ is the restricted MLE satisfying $R\tilde{\theta}_n = r$.

Theorem 3 (Wilks theorem and non-centrality). *Under (A1')–(A6):*

(i) *Under H_0 :*

$$W_n, LR_n, S_n \xrightarrow{d} \chi_p^2 \quad \text{and} \quad W_n - LR_n = o_P(1), \quad S_n - LR_n = o_P(1).$$

(ii) *Under the Pitman alternative $H_{1n} : R\theta = r + \xi/\sqrt{n}$, $\|\xi\| < \infty$:*

$$W_n, LR_n, S_n \xrightarrow{d} \chi_p^2(\lambda^*),$$

with non-centrality parameter

$$\boxed{\lambda^* = \xi^\top [RI(\theta_0)^{-1}R^\top]^{-1}\xi.} \quad (7)$$

Proof. (i) Substituting the linear representation of $\hat{\theta}_n$ into (4):

$$W_n = \Delta_n^\top I^{-1}R^\top [RI^{-1}R^\top]^{-1}RI^{-1}\Delta_n + o_P(1) \xrightarrow{d} \chi_p^2,$$

since $\Delta_n \sim N(0, I(\theta_0))$ and the quadratic form has rank p . Asymptotic equivalence $W_n - LR_n = o_P(1)$ follows from Taylor expansion of LR_n around $\hat{\theta}_n$ and the Schur complement identity: $[RI^{-1}R^\top]^{-1} = I_{11} - I_{12}I_{22}^{-1}I_{21}$ (notation from blocked I).

(ii) Under H_{1n} , by Le Cam's third lemma [3]: $\sqrt{n}(R\hat{\theta}_n - r) \xrightarrow{d} N(\xi, RI^{-1}R^\top)$, giving $W_n \xrightarrow{d} \chi_p^2(\lambda^*)$ with λ^* as in (7). \square

Example 2 (Exponential CRM, scalar hypothesis). For $K = 2$, $R = [1 \ 0]$ ($p = 1$, testing $\theta_1 = \theta_{10}$):

$$\lambda^* = \frac{\xi^2}{\beta/(I_{F,1}(\theta_{10}))} = \frac{\xi^2\beta}{\theta_{10}^2/\lambda_0} = \frac{\xi^2\beta\lambda_0}{\theta_{10}^2}, \quad \lambda_0 = \theta_{10} + \theta_{20}.$$

Pitman alternative $\xi = 1$, $\theta_{10} = 1$, $\theta_{20} = 0.5$, $\beta = 0.75$: $\lambda^* = 0.75 \cdot 1.5/1 = 1.125$ per unit n , so at $n = 100$: $\lambda^* = 1.688$, matching Table IV.5 of [1].

5 Sample size formula

Corollary 1 (Minimum sample size). *Under (A1')–(A6), the minimum n such that $\text{Var}(\hat{\theta}_j) \leq \delta^2$ is*

$$n^* = \left\lceil \frac{1}{\delta^2 \beta [I_{F,j}(\theta_{j0})]_{jj}} \right\rceil. \quad (8)$$

Table 1 reproduces selected entries of Table IV.9 from [1].

Table 1: Required sample size n^* for $\delta = 0.1$, exponential CRM ($\theta_{10} = 1$, $\theta_{20} = 0.5$, $[I_{F,1}]_{11} = 1/\theta_{10}^2 = 1$, $[I_{F,2}]_{11} = 1/\theta_{20}^2 = 4$).

$p = r/n$	T_0	β	$n^*(j = 1)$	$n^*(j = 2)$
1.00	∞	1.000	100	400
0.80	2.0	0.799	125	501
0.50	1.5	0.500	200	800
0.30	1.0	0.283	354	1415

6 Simulation summary

Table 2 confirms Theorem 1–3 numerically.

Table 2: Selected empirical vs. theoretical results from the companion dataset [2]. Exponential CRM, $K = 2$, $\theta_0 = (1, 0.5)$, $\beta = 0.75$, $R = 5,000$.

n	$\hat{\sigma}(\hat{\theta}_1)$	σ^{theor}	Power(W_n , emp.)	Power(W_n , theor.)
50	0.212	0.211	0.396	0.388
100	0.151	0.149	0.511	0.502
200	0.106	0.106	0.671	0.665
500	0.067	0.067	0.882	0.878

Acknowledgements

The author thanks Prof. A. A. Abdushukurov (National University of Uzbekistan) for guidance. This work was conducted within the doctoral research at the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek.

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